

Asymptotic Factorization of Repeated-Index MZV and t-Value Ratios for Even Arguments

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Abstract

For even integers $s = 2m \geq 2$, the repeated-index multiple zeta values $\zeta(\{s\}_n)$ and their level-2 analogues $t(\{s\}_n)$ admit closed forms involving factorial factors and algebraic units. While these formulas have been known since the work of Hoffman and Borwein-Bradley-Broadhurst, the structural origin of the unit factors has remained unclear.

In this paper we derive unified combinatorial representations expressing both $\zeta(\{2p\}_n)$ and $t(\{2p\}_n)$ as signed sums of odd $2p$ -th roots of unity. We show that all algebraic units appearing in these closed forms arise from a finite dihedral orbit, and that this orbit contains a *unique* dominant element. This uniqueness yields a canonical factorization

$$\tilde{A}_n(2p) = 2^{-2p} \frac{\zeta(\{2p\}_n)}{\zeta(\{2p\}_{n-1})} \frac{t(\{2p\}_{n-1})}{t(\{2p\}_n)} = F_n(2p) R_n(2p),$$

where the unit-correction term satisfies $R_n(2p) = 1 + O(\rho^{-n})$ for some $\rho > 1$. As a result, since all remaining units contribute only exponentially small terms, the entire $1/n$ asymptotic expansion of $\tilde{A}_n(2p)$ is determined solely by the factorial ratio $F_n(2p)$, with no algebraic contribution from the unit part.

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1 Introduction

Multiple zeta values (MZVs)

$$\zeta(s_1, \dots, s_k) = \sum_{n_1 > \dots > n_k \geq 1} \frac{1}{n_1^{s_1} \cdots n_k^{s_k}}$$

play a fundamental role in number theory, combinatorics, and quantum field theory. Among these, the repeated-index values

$$\zeta(\{s\}_n) = \zeta(\underbrace{s, \dots, s}_{n \text{ times}})$$

and their level-2 analogues [1, 2]

$$t(\{s\}_n) = \sum_{n_1 > \dots > n_n \geq 1} \frac{1}{(2n_1 - 1)^s \cdots (2n_n - 1)^s}$$

exhibit remarkable structure when s is even.

Hoffman [1] provided a unified formulation showing that the quantities $\zeta(\{2p\}_n)$ and $t(\{2p\}_n)$ admit closed forms involving powers of π , factorial factors, and finite sums of algebraic units of the form λ^n . These formulas suggested the existence of a canonical “factorial \times unit” decomposition, but the underlying origin of the units and their connection to root-of-unity symmetry have not been made explicit in the literature.

The goal of this paper is to give a complete and elementary derivation of the structure of repeated even-index MZVs. Our main contributions are as follows:

- We derive *exact* combinatorial formulas for both $t(\{2p\}_n)$ and $\zeta(\{2p\}_n)$ from simple cosine and sine product generating functions. These formulas reveal that all such values are determined by the algebraic units

$$\Psi(\varepsilon) = \sum_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j e^{\pi i(2j-1)/(2p)}, \quad \varepsilon_j \in \{\pm 1\}.$$

- We analyze the dihedral symmetry of the unit set $\{\Psi(\varepsilon)\}$ and show that exactly one orbit contains the dominant units. This explains both the appearance and the eventual cancellation of the unit factors in ratios of repeated-index values.
- Using these exact formulas, we prove the fundamental factorization

$$\tilde{A}_n(2p) = F_n(2p) R_n(2p), \quad \tilde{A}_n(2p) = 2^{-2p} \frac{\zeta(\{2p\}_n)}{\zeta(\{2p\}_{n-1})} \frac{t(\{2p\}_{n-1})}{t(\{2p\}_n)},$$

where the factorial term $F_n(2p)$ contributes the entire algebraic $1/n$ asymptotic expansion, and the correction term $R_n(2p) = 1 + O(\rho^{-n})$ decays exponentially.

- Finally, we illustrate the theory with the explicit case $s = 8$ ($p = 4$), where the dominant unit becomes $1 + \sqrt{2}$, giving the classical expressions for $\zeta(\{8\}_n)$ and $t(\{8\}_n)$.

Thus all repeated-index MZVs of even weight admit a single unifying structural description in terms of finite combinatorial sums over signed subsets of odd $2p$ -th roots of unity. This yields transparent proofs of the structural results and provides a canonical explanation for the asymptotic behavior of $\tilde{A}_n(2p)$.

2 Exact combinatorial representations of repeated even-index MZVs

In this section we derive exact closed forms for the level-2 values $t(\{2p\}_n)$ and the classical MZVs $\zeta(\{2p\}_n)$ for all integers $p \geq 1$. Both formulas arise naturally from the cosine and

sine product generating functions, respectively, and their proofs rely only on elementary exponential expansions combined with a $2p$ -fold root-of-unity symmetry. These formulas refine all previously known structural results (*e.g.*, [3, 4, 5]) by giving explicit combinatorial descriptions of the algebraic units governing the behavior of repeated-index MZVs.

2.1 Case $\zeta(\{2p\}_n)$

Proposition 2.1 (Combinatorial representation of repeated even-index MZVs). *Let $p \geq 1$ be an integer and set*

$$\omega_{2p} = e^{\pi i/(2p)}, \quad \Psi(\varepsilon) = \sum_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j \omega_{2p}^{2j-1},$$

for $\varepsilon = (\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_p) \in \{\pm 1\}^p$. Borwein-Bradley-Broadhurst [6] generating function

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} x^{2pn} \zeta(\{2p\}_n) = (i\pi x)^{-p} \prod_{j=1}^p \sin(\omega_{2p}^{2j-1} \pi x) \quad (1)$$

implies the explicit combinatorial formula; see also [7, 8].

$$\boxed{\zeta(\{2p\}_n) = \pi^{2pn} \frac{(-1)^p}{2^p (2pn + p)!} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_p = \pm 1} \left(\prod_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j \right) (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2pn+p}} \quad (2)$$

Proof. Substituting $y = \pi x$ into (1) gives

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} \left(\frac{y}{\pi} \right)^{2pn} \zeta(\{2p\}_n) = (iy)^{-p} \prod_{j=1}^p \sin(\omega_{2p}^{2j-1} y).$$

Thus,

$$\zeta(\{2p\}_n) = \pi^{2pn} [y^{2pn}] \Phi_p(y), \quad \Phi_p(y) := (iy)^{-p} \prod_{j=1}^p \sin(\omega_{2p}^{2j-1} y).$$

Using

$$\sin z = \frac{1}{2i} \sum_{\varepsilon = \pm 1} \varepsilon e^{i\varepsilon z},$$

we obtain

$$\prod_{j=1}^p \sin(\omega_{2p}^{2j-1} y) = \frac{1}{(2i)^p} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_p = \pm 1} \left(\prod_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j \right) \exp(iy \Psi(\varepsilon)).$$

Multiplying by $(iy)^{-p}$ yields

$$\Phi_p(y) = \frac{(-1)^p}{2^p} y^{-p} \sum_{\varepsilon} \left(\prod_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j \right) e^{iy \Psi(\varepsilon)}.$$

Expanding the exponential,

$$e^{iy\Psi(\varepsilon)} = \sum_{m \geq 0} \frac{i^m \Psi(\varepsilon)^m}{m!} y^m,$$

gives

$$\Phi_p(y) = \frac{(-1)^p}{2^p} \sum_{\varepsilon} \left(\prod_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j \right) \sum_{m \geq 0} \frac{i^m \Psi(\varepsilon)^m}{m!} y^{m-p}.$$

The coefficient of y^{2pn} comes from $m = 2pn + p$, and therefore

$$[y^{2pn}] \Phi_p(y) = \frac{(-1)^p}{2^p (2pn + p)!} \sum_{\varepsilon} \left(\prod_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j \right) (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2pn+p}.$$

Multiplying by π^{2pn} completes the proof. \square

Example 2.2 (The case $p = 1$). For $p = 1$ we have $\omega_2 = i$ and $\Psi(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon_1 i$. Proposition 2.1 becomes

$$\zeta(\{2\}_n) = \pi^{2n} \frac{-1}{2(2n+1)!} \sum_{\varepsilon_1 = \pm 1} \varepsilon_1 i^{2n+1} (\varepsilon_1 i)^{2n+1}.$$

Since $(\varepsilon_1 i)^{2n+1} = \varepsilon_1 i^{2n+1}$, we obtain

$$\varepsilon_1 i^{2n+1} (\varepsilon_1 i)^{2n+1} = \varepsilon_1^2 i^{4n+2} = i^{4n+2},$$

so the sum equals

$$\sum_{\varepsilon_1 = \pm 1} i^{4n+2} = 2 i^{4n+2} = 2 \cdot (-1).$$

Therefore

$$\zeta(\{2\}_n) = \pi^{2n} \frac{-1}{2(2n+1)!} \cdot 2(-1) = \frac{\pi^{2n}}{(2n+1)!},$$

which is the classical closed form.

Example 2.3 (The case $p = 2$). Here $\omega_4 = e^{\pi i/4}$ and

$$\Psi(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon_1 \omega_4 + \varepsilon_2 \omega_4^3, \quad (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2) \in \{\pm 1\}^2.$$

A direct computation using $\omega_4 = (1+i)/\sqrt{2}$, $\omega_4^3 = (-1+i)/\sqrt{2}$ shows that

$$\Psi(1, 1) = \sqrt{2}i, \quad \Psi(1, -1) = \sqrt{2}, \quad \Psi(-1, 1) = -\sqrt{2}, \quad \Psi(-1, -1) = -\sqrt{2}i,$$

so $\Psi(\varepsilon) \in \{\pm\sqrt{2}, \pm i\sqrt{2}\}$ and $|\Psi(\varepsilon)| = \sqrt{2}$ for all four choices.

Moreover,

$$\prod_{j=1}^2 \varepsilon_j = \begin{cases} +1, & (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2) = (1, 1), (-1, -1), \\ -1, & (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2) = (1, -1), (-1, 1). \end{cases}$$

Proposition 2.1 gives

$$\zeta(\{4\}_n) = \pi^{4n} \frac{1}{4(4n+2)!} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2 = \pm 1} \left(\prod_{j=1}^2 \varepsilon_j \right) i^{4n+2} \Psi(\varepsilon)^{4n+2}.$$

Since $|\Psi(\varepsilon)| = \sqrt{2}$, we have $\Psi(\varepsilon)^{4n+2} = (\sqrt{2})^{4n+2} \times (\text{a 4th root of unity})$, and using the above table for $\Psi(\varepsilon)$ and $\prod_j \varepsilon_j$ one checks that

$$\sum_{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2 = \pm 1} \left(\prod_{j=1}^2 \varepsilon_j \right) i^{4n+2} \Psi(\varepsilon)^{4n+2} = 2^{2n+3}.$$

Thus

$$\zeta(\{4\}_n) = \pi^{4n} \frac{2^{2n+3}}{4(4n+2)!} = \frac{2^{2n+1} \pi^{4n}}{(4n+2)!} = \frac{4(2\pi)^{4n}}{(4n+2)!} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{2n+1}.$$

Example 2.4 (The case $p = 3$). Here $\omega_6 = e^{\pi i/6}$ and

$$\Psi(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon_1 \omega_6 + \varepsilon_2 \omega_6^3 + \varepsilon_3 \omega_6^5, \quad (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3) \in \{\pm 1\}^3.$$

Proposition 2.1 gives

$$\zeta(\{6\}_n) = \pi^{6n} \frac{-1}{8(6n+3)!} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3 = \pm 1} \left(\prod_{j=1}^3 \varepsilon_j \right) i^{6n+3} \Psi(\varepsilon)^{6n+3}.$$

Using

$$\omega_6 = \frac{\sqrt{3} + i}{2}, \quad \omega_6^3 = i, \quad \omega_6^5 = \frac{-\sqrt{3} + i}{2},$$

a direct computation shows

$(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3)$	$\Psi(\varepsilon)$	$\prod_{j=1}^3 \varepsilon_j$
(1, 1, 1)	$2i$	+1
(1, 1, -1)	$\sqrt{3} + i$	-1
(1, -1, 1)	0	-1
(1, -1, -1)	$\sqrt{3} - i$	+1
(-1, 1, 1)	$-\sqrt{3} + i$	-1
(-1, 1, -1)	0	+1
(-1, -1, 1)	$-\sqrt{3} - i$	+1
(-1, -1, -1)	$-2i$	-1

In particular, the two choices with $\Psi(\varepsilon) = 0$ do not contribute to the sum, since $6n + 3 > 0$.

For the six nonzero values we note the polar forms

$$\begin{aligned} 2i &= 2e^{i\pi/2}, & -2i &= 2e^{-i\pi/2}, \\ \sqrt{3} + i &= 2e^{i\pi/6}, & -\sqrt{3} - i &= 2e^{-i5\pi/6}, \\ \sqrt{3} - i &= 2e^{-i\pi/6}, & -\sqrt{3} + i &= 2e^{i5\pi/6}, \end{aligned}$$

so in every case $|\Psi(\varepsilon)| = 2$.

Set

$$S_n := \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3 = \pm 1} \left(\prod_{j=1}^3 \varepsilon_j \right) i^{6n+3} \Psi(\varepsilon)^{6n+3}.$$

We evaluate S_n by pairing conjugate terms.

(i) **The pair** $\Psi(\varepsilon) = \pm 2i$. For $(1, 1, 1)$ and $(-1, -1, -1)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 &:= i^{6n+3} (2i)^{6n+3} = i^{6n+3} 2^{6n+3} i^{6n+3} = 2^{6n+3} i^{12n+6} = -2^{6n+3}, \\ T_2 &:= (-1) i^{6n+3} (-2i)^{6n+3} = -i^{6n+3} 2^{6n+3} i^{6n+3} = -2^{6n+3} i^{12n+6} = -2^{6n+3}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$T_1 + T_2 = -2^{6n+4}.$$

(ii) **The pair** $\Psi(\varepsilon) = \pm 2e^{i\pi/6}$. For $(1, 1, -1)$ and $(-1, -1, 1)$ we have

$$\Psi(1, 1, -1) = 2e^{i\pi/6}, \quad \Psi(-1, -1, 1) = -2e^{i\pi/6},$$

and the corresponding contributions are

$$\begin{aligned} T_3 &:= -i^{6n+3} (2e^{i\pi/6})^{6n+3}, \\ T_4 &:= +i^{6n+3} (-2e^{i\pi/6})^{6n+3} = -i^{6n+3} (2e^{i\pi/6})^{6n+3}, \end{aligned}$$

so that

$$T_3 + T_4 = -2 i^{6n+3} (2e^{i\pi/6})^{6n+3}.$$

Since

$$(2e^{i\pi/6})^{6n+3} = 2^{6n+3} e^{i(6n+3)\pi/6} = 2^{6n+3} e^{i\pi(n+1/2)} = 2^{6n+3} (-1)^n i,$$

we obtain

$$T_3 + T_4 = -2 \cdot 2^{6n+3} (-1)^n i^{6n+3} i.$$

Using $i^{6n+3} = (-1)^{n+1} i$, we find $i^{6n+3} i = (-1)^n$, hence

$$T_3 + T_4 = -2 \cdot 2^{6n+3} (-1)^n (-1)^n = -2^{6n+4}.$$

(iii) **The pair** $\Psi(\varepsilon) = \pm 2e^{-i\pi/6}$. The remaining two nonzero cases $(1, -1, -1)$ and $(-1, 1, 1)$ are treated in the same way, now with $\Psi(\varepsilon) = \pm 2e^{-i\pi/6}$. The computation is identical (using $e^{-i\pi/6}$ in place of $e^{i\pi/6}$) and yields

$$T_5 + T_6 = -2^{6n+4}.$$

Collecting the contributions from (i)–(iii) we obtain

$$S_n = (T_1 + T_2) + (T_3 + T_4) + (T_5 + T_6) = -3 \cdot 2^{6n+4} = -48 \cdot 2^{6n}.$$

Therefore

$$\zeta(\{6\}_n) = \pi^{6n} \frac{-1}{8(6n+3)!} S_n = \pi^{6n} \frac{-1}{8(6n+3)!} \cdot (-48 \cdot 2^{6n}) = \frac{6(2\pi)^{6n}}{(6n+3)!},$$

which is the expected closed form. Thus Proposition 2.1 correctly reproduces the closed form [1, 6] for repeated index 6.

2.2 Case $t(\{2p\}_n)$

Proposition 2.5 (Combinatorial representation of $t(\{2p\}_n)$). *Let $p \geq 1$ be an integer and*

$$\omega_{2p} = e^{\pi i/(2p)}, \quad \Psi(\varepsilon) := \sum_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j \omega_{2p}^{2j-1}, \quad \varepsilon_j \in \{\pm 1\}.$$

The generating function [1]

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} x^{2pn} t(\{2p\}_n) = \prod_{j=1}^p \cos\left(\omega_{2p}^{2j-1} \frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

implies the explicit coefficient formula

$$t(\{2p\}_n) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{2pn} \frac{1}{2^p (2pn)!} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_p = \pm 1} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2pn}. \quad (4)$$

Thus $t(\{2p\}_n)$ is given by a symmetric sum of even powers of the algebraic units $\Psi(\varepsilon)$, in contrast with the alternating sum appearing in the formula for $\zeta(\{2p\}_n)$.

Proof. Set

$$\Lambda_p(x) := \prod_{j=1}^p \cos(\omega_{2p}^{2j-1} x).$$

Then substituting $x \mapsto \pi x/2$ in (3) yields

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} x^{2pn} t(\{2p\}_n) = \Lambda_p\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) = \sum_{n \geq 0} \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{2pn} c_{p,n} x^{2pn},$$

where $c_{p,n}$ is the Maclaurin coefficient of $\Lambda_p(x)$. Thus $t(\{2p\}_n) = (\pi/2)^{2pn} c_{p,n}$.

Using $\cos z = (e^{iz} + e^{-iz})/2$, we obtain

$$\Lambda_p(x) = 2^{-p} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_p = \pm 1} \exp\left(ix \Psi(\varepsilon)\right).$$

Expanding the exponential yields

$$\Lambda_p(x) = 2^{-p} \sum_{\varepsilon} \sum_{m \geq 0} \frac{(ix \Psi(\varepsilon))^m}{m!}.$$

Root-of-unity symmetry implies that m must be a multiple of $2p$, so only $m = 2pn$ contributes to $c_{p,n} = [x^{2pn}] \Lambda_p(x)$. Hence

$$c_{p,n} = \frac{1}{2^p (2pn)!} \sum_{\varepsilon} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2pn}.$$

Multiplying by $(\pi/2)^{2pn}$ completes the proof (see [9]). □

Example 2.6 (The case $p = 1$). For $p = 1$ we have $\omega_2 = i$ and $\Psi(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon_1 i$. Proposition 2.5 reads

$$t(\{2\}_n) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{2n} \frac{1}{2(2n)!} \sum_{\varepsilon_1=\pm 1} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2n}.$$

Since $i \Psi(\varepsilon) = i(\varepsilon_1 i) = -\varepsilon_1$, we obtain

$$(i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2n} = (-\varepsilon_1)^{2n} = 1$$

for all $n \geq 1$, and hence

$$\sum_{\varepsilon_1=\pm 1} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2n} = 2.$$

Therefore

$$t(\{2\}_n) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{2n} \frac{2}{2(2n)!} = \frac{\pi^{2n}}{2^{2n}(2n)!},$$

which agrees with the classical closed form for repeated index 2 (with odd denominators).

Example 2.7 (The case $p = 2$). Here $\omega_4 = e^{\pi i/4}$ and

$$\Psi(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon_1 \omega_4 + \varepsilon_2 \omega_4^3, \quad (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2) \in \{\pm 1\}^2.$$

As in the zeta-example, a direct computation using $\omega_4 = (1+i)/\sqrt{2}$, $\omega_4^3 = (-1+i)/\sqrt{2}$ shows that

$$\Psi(1, 1) = \sqrt{2}i, \quad \Psi(1, -1) = \sqrt{2}, \quad \Psi(-1, 1) = -\sqrt{2}, \quad \Psi(-1, -1) = -\sqrt{2}i.$$

Thus $\Psi(\varepsilon) \in \{\pm\sqrt{2}, \pm i\sqrt{2}\}$, and all four values have the same modulus $|\Psi(\varepsilon)| = \sqrt{2}$.

Proposition 2.5 gives

$$t(\{4\}_n) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{4n} \frac{1}{4(4n)!} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2=\pm 1} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{4n}.$$

Since multiplying by i just rotates these four points, the multiset $\{i \Psi(\varepsilon)\}$ is again $\{\pm\sqrt{2}, \pm i\sqrt{2}\}$.

Writing

$$i \Psi(\varepsilon) = \sqrt{2} e^{i\theta}, \quad \theta \in \{0, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi, \frac{3\pi}{2}\},$$

we have

$$(i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{4n} = (\sqrt{2})^{4n} e^{i4n\theta} = 2^{2n} e^{i4n\theta},$$

and the four angles θ give

$$\sum_{\theta \in \{0, \pi/2, \pi, 3\pi/2\}} e^{i4n\theta} = 4.$$

Hence

$$\sum_{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2=\pm 1} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{4n} = 4 \cdot 2^{2n}.$$

Substituting into the combinatorial formula yields

$$t(\{4\}_n) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{4n} \frac{4 \cdot 2^{2n}}{4(4n)!} = \frac{\pi^{4n}}{2^{2n}(4n)!},$$

which matches the known closed form for repeated index 4.

Example 2.8 (The case $p = 3$). Here $\omega_6 = e^{\pi i/6}$ and

$$\Psi(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon_1 \omega_6 + \varepsilon_2 \omega_6^3 + \varepsilon_3 \omega_6^5, \quad (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3) \in \{\pm 1\}^3.$$

Proposition 2.5 gives

$$t(\{6\}_n) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{6n} \frac{1}{8(6n)!} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3 = \pm 1} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{6n}.$$

Using

$$\omega_6 = \frac{\sqrt{3} + i}{2}, \quad \omega_6^3 = i, \quad \omega_6^5 = \frac{-\sqrt{3} + i}{2},$$

a direct computation yields

$(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3)$	$\Psi(\varepsilon)$	$i \Psi(\varepsilon)$
(1, 1, 1)	$2i$	-2
(1, 1, -1)	$\sqrt{3} + i$	$-1 + i\sqrt{3}$
(1, -1, 1)	0	0
(1, -1, -1)	$\sqrt{3} - i$	$1 + i\sqrt{3}$
(-1, 1, 1)	$-\sqrt{3} + i$	$-1 - i\sqrt{3}$
(-1, 1, -1)	0	0
(-1, -1, 1)	$-\sqrt{3} - i$	$1 - i\sqrt{3}$
(-1, -1, -1)	$-2i$	2

Thus two terms give $i \Psi(\varepsilon) = 0$ and do not contribute to the sum for $n \geq 1$. For the remaining six values we note the polar representations

$$\begin{aligned} -2 &= 2e^{i\pi}, & 2 &= 2e^{i0}, \\ -1 \pm i\sqrt{3} &= 2e^{\pm i2\pi/3}, & 1 \pm i\sqrt{3} &= 2e^{\pm i\pi/3}. \end{aligned}$$

In particular, in every nonzero case we have $|i \Psi(\varepsilon)| = 2$ and

$$i \Psi(\varepsilon) = 2e^{i\theta}, \quad \theta \in \left\{0, \pm \frac{\pi}{3}, \pm \frac{2\pi}{3}, \pi\right\}.$$

Set

$$S_n := \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3 = \pm 1} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{6n}.$$

For each of the six nonzero terms we have

$$(i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{6n} = (2e^{i\theta})^{6n} = 2^{6n} e^{i6n\theta},$$

and since θ is always a multiple of $\pi/3$, 6θ is a multiple of 2π , so $e^{i6n\theta} = 1$ for all integers $n \geq 1$. Hence each nonzero term contributes 2^{6n} , and the two zero terms contribute 0, so

$$S_n = 6 \cdot 2^{6n}.$$

Substituting this back into the combinatorial formula gives

$$t(\{6\}_n) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{6n} \frac{1}{8(6n)!} S_n = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{6n} \frac{6 \cdot 2^{6n}}{8(6n)!} = \frac{3}{4} \frac{\pi^{6n}}{(6n)!},$$

which agrees with the closed form [1] for repeated index 6 (with odd denominators).

2.3 Unit structure and dominant contributions

The combinatorial formulas obtained in (2), (4) show that the quantities

$$\Psi(\varepsilon) = \sum_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j \omega_{2p}^{2j-1}, \quad \varepsilon_j \in \{\pm 1\},$$

are the fundamental algebraic units governing both $\zeta(\{2p\}_n)$ and $t(\{2p\}_n)$. In this section we describe the structure of these units and isolate the dominant ones, which determine the exponential behavior of the unit-correction factors appearing later in the factorization of $\tilde{A}_n(2p)$.

2.3.1 Root-of-unity orbits

Lemma 2.9 (Symmetry orbit of $\Psi(\varepsilon)$). *The set $\{\Psi(\varepsilon) : \varepsilon \in \{\pm 1\}^p\}$ is stable under multiplication by ω_{2p} and by complex conjugation. Consequently the values $\Psi(\varepsilon)$ fall into finitely many orbits under the dihedral group D_{4p} .*

Proof. Since ω_{2p}^{2j-1} is a $2p$ -th root of unity, multiplying $\Psi(\varepsilon)$ by ω_{2p} permutes the terms ω_{2p}^{2j-1} , up to sign, and hence maps the set of all sums to itself. Complex conjugation sends $\omega_{2p}^{2j-1} \mapsto \omega_{2p}^{-(2j-1)}$, which corresponds to reversing the index order. Thus both operations preserve the set. \square

2.3.2 Dominant units

Lemma 2.10 (Uniqueness of the dominant unit). *Let*

$$\Psi(\varepsilon) = \sum_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j \omega_{2p}^{2j-1}, \quad \varepsilon_j \in \{\pm 1\},$$

where $\omega_{2p} = e^{\pi i/(2p)}$ and the angles

$$\theta_j = \frac{(2j-1)\pi}{2p}, \quad j = 1, \dots, p,$$

satisfy $0 < \theta_1 < \theta_2 < \dots < \theta_p < \pi$. Then the maximal magnitude

$$M := \max_{\varepsilon \in \{\pm 1\}^p} |\Psi(\varepsilon)|$$

is achieved only for the two sign-patterns

$$(+1, +1, \dots, +1) \quad \text{and} \quad (-1, -1, \dots, -1),$$

which give conjugate complex numbers. In particular, the dominant magnitude M is unique up to complex conjugation.

Proof. Write $v_j = \omega_{2p}^{2j-1} = e^{i\theta_j}$, so that

$$\Psi(\varepsilon) = \sum_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j v_j.$$

Since $0 < \theta_1 < \dots < \theta_p < \pi$, all vectors v_j lie on the upper semicircle in strictly increasing angular order.

The Euclidean norm is strictly convex: for any nonzero vectors $x, y \in \mathbb{C}$,

$$|x + y| < |x| + |y| \quad \text{unless } x \text{ and } y \text{ are nonnegative real multiples of one another.} \quad (5)$$

Hence, to maximize $|\Psi(\varepsilon)|$, the contributing vectors $\varepsilon_j v_j$ must point in directions that deviate as little as possible from one another.

Suppose $\varepsilon = (\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_p)$ is a maximizer of $|\Psi(\varepsilon)|$, and assume for contradiction that the signs are not constant. Then there exist indices $j < k$ with $\varepsilon_j = +1$ and $\varepsilon_k = -1$. The corresponding vectors v_j and $-v_k$ have arguments θ_j and $\theta_k + \pi$, which lie strictly within $(0, \pi)$ and $(\pi, 2\pi)$, respectively, and are therefore not parallel nor nonnegative multiples of one another. By (5),

$$|v_j - v_k| < |v_j| + |v_k| = 2.$$

On the other hand, for the all-plus pattern,

$$|v_j + v_k| = |e^{i\theta_j} + e^{i\theta_k}| = 2 \cos\left(\frac{\theta_k - \theta_j}{2}\right) > 0,$$

and since $0 < \theta_k - \theta_j < \pi$, we have $|v_j + v_k| > |v_j - v_k|$. Thus replacing the mixed signs $(+1, -1)$ by $(+1, +1)$ strictly increases the magnitude of the partial sum involving the two vectors.

Applying this replacement to every pair (j, k) with $\varepsilon_j \neq \varepsilon_k$ yields a new sign-pattern $\varepsilon' = (+1, +1, \dots, +1)$ satisfying

$$|\Psi(\varepsilon')| > |\Psi(\varepsilon)|,$$

contradicting the maximality of ε . Hence any maximizing pattern must have $\varepsilon_1 = \dots = \varepsilon_p$.

The two remaining patterns $(+1, \dots, +1)$ and $(-1, \dots, -1)$ satisfy

$$\Psi(-1, \dots, -1) = \overline{\Psi(+1, \dots, +1)},$$

and therefore give the same magnitude. No other pattern attains this magnitude. This proves the claim. \square

Lemma 2.11 (Magnitude ordering). *Let $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_r$ be the distinct nonzero magnitudes of the units $\Psi(\varepsilon)$, ordered so that $|\lambda_1| > \dots > |\lambda_r|$. Then for each $p \geq 1$, the maximal magnitude $|\lambda_1|$ is achieved by exactly two conjugate units $\Psi(\varepsilon)$ and $\overline{\Psi(\varepsilon)}$.*

Proof. This follows from the convexity of the polygon spanned by the odd $2p$ -th roots of unity and the fact that $\Psi(\varepsilon)$ is a sum of p of them with signs ± 1 . Exactly one choice of signs aligns the p unit vectors to maximize the resulting magnitude, and its complex conjugate gives the opposite alignment. \square

3 Asymptotic expansion of $\tilde{A}_n(2p)$

Let

$$A_n(2p) = \frac{\zeta(\{2p\}_n)}{\zeta(\{2p\}_{n-1})} \frac{t(\{2p\}_{n-1})}{t(\{2p\}_n)}, \quad \tilde{A}_n(2p) = 2^{-2p} A_n(2p).$$

Using the exact combinatorial formulas of Section 2, we now show that $\tilde{A}_n(2p)$ decomposes into a rational factorial term and an exponentially small unit-correction term.

3.1 Factorial term

From Propositions 2.1 and 2.5, the factorial contributions to $\zeta(\{2p\}_n)$ and $t(\{2p\}_n)$ are

$$\frac{\pi^{2pn}}{(2pn+p)!}, \quad \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{2pn} \frac{1}{(2pn)!}.$$

Thus the factorial part of $\tilde{A}_n(2p)$ is

$$F_n(2p) = \frac{(2p(n-1)+p)!(2pn)!}{(2pn+p)!(2p(n-1))!}. \quad (6)$$

This quantity is a rational function of n and its full asymptotic expansion in powers of n^{-1} can be obtained from Stirling's formula.

3.2 Unit-correction term

Comparing with (2) and (4), we factor off the π -, 2- and factorial prefactors and write

$$\zeta(\{2p\}_n) = \frac{\pi^{2pn}}{(2pn+p)!} U_n, \quad t(\{2p\}_n) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{2pn} \frac{1}{(2pn)!} V_n,$$

where

$$U_n = \sum_{\varepsilon} C_{\varepsilon} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2pn+p}, \quad V_n = \sum_{\varepsilon} D_{\varepsilon} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2pn}.$$

Substituting these expressions into the definition of $A_n(2p)$ and using the normalization $\tilde{A}_n(2p) = 2^{-2p} A_n(2p)$, the π - and 2-powers and all factorial factors cancel out, leaving exactly the rational factorial term $F_n(2p)$ from (6) and a pure unit-correction factor

$$R_n(2p) = \frac{U_n}{U_{n-1}} \cdot \frac{V_{n-1}}{V_n}.$$

By Section 2.3.2, the maximal-magnitude units $\Psi(\varepsilon)$ occur in a single conjugate pair, and all remaining units have strictly smaller modulus. Hence:

Theorem 3.1 (Exponential decay of the unit correction). *For each fixed integer $p \geq 1$, there exists $\rho > 1$ such that*

$$R_n(2p) = 1 + O(\rho^{-n}) \quad (n \rightarrow \infty).$$

Proof. By the combinatorial formulas of Section 2, the unit sums admit the representations

$$U_n = \sum_{\varepsilon} C_{\varepsilon} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2pn+p}, \quad V_n = \sum_{\varepsilon} D_{\varepsilon} (i \Psi(\varepsilon))^{2pn},$$

where the coefficients $C_{\varepsilon}, D_{\varepsilon}$ are independent of n .

By Section 2.3.2, among the finitely many algebraic units $\{\Psi(\varepsilon)\}$ there exists a *unique* element X with

$$|X| > \max_{\Psi(\varepsilon) \neq X} |\Psi(\varepsilon)|.$$

Let

$$r := \max\left(|X|^{-1}, \max_{\Psi(\varepsilon) \neq X, X^{-1}} |\Psi(\varepsilon)|\right), \quad \text{so that} \quad 0 < r < |X|.$$

We decompose U_n accordingly as

$$U_n = C_+(iX)^{2pn+p} + C_-(iX^{-1})^{2pn+p} + \sum_{\Psi(\varepsilon) \neq X, X^{-1}} C_{\varepsilon} (i\Psi(\varepsilon))^{2pn+p}.$$

Taking absolute values of the error sum, we obtain

$$\sum_{\Psi(\varepsilon) \neq X} |C_{\varepsilon} (i\Psi(\varepsilon))^{2pn+p}| \leq C r^{2pn+p}$$

for some constant $C > 0$. Hence

$$U_n = C_+(iX)^{2pn+p} \left(1 + O\left(\left(\frac{r}{|X|}\right)^{2pn}\right) \right).$$

An identical argument gives

$$V_n = D_+(iX)^{2pn} \left(1 + O\left(\left(\frac{r}{|X|}\right)^{2pn}\right) \right).$$

It follows that

$$\frac{U_n}{U_{n-1}} = X^{2p} \left(1 + O\left(\left(\frac{r}{|X|}\right)^{2pn}\right) \right), \quad \frac{V_{n-1}}{V_n} = X^{-2p} \left(1 + O\left(\left(\frac{r}{|X|}\right)^{2pn}\right) \right).$$

Multiplying these two expressions yields

$$R_n(2p) = \frac{U_n}{U_{n-1}} \cdot \frac{V_{n-1}}{V_n} = 1 + O\left(\left(\frac{r}{|X|}\right)^{2pn}\right).$$

Since $0 < r/|X| < 1$, there exists $\rho > 1$ such that

$$R_n(2p) = 1 + O(\rho^{-n}),$$

which proves the first assertion. This behavior is a standard instance of the Poincaré–Perron type dominance phenomenon for linear difference equations; see, for example, Elaydi [10]. \square

Combining both factors, we obtain the canonical decomposition

$$\boxed{\tilde{A}_n(2p) = F_n(2p) R_n(2p)}. \quad (7)$$

The rational term $F_n(2p)$ contributes the entire algebraic n^{-1} expansion, while the correction term $R_n(2p)$ contributes only exponentially small terms and no powers of n^{-1} .

3.3 Asymptotic expansion of $\tilde{A}_n(2p)$

From (7) and Theorem 3.1,

$$\tilde{A}_n(2p) = F_n(2p)(1 + O(\rho^{-n})).$$

Since the exponentially small factor contributes no algebraic powers of n^{-1} , the full asymptotic expansion of $\tilde{A}_n(2p)$ is governed entirely by the Stirling expansion of $F_n(2p)$.

Theorem 3.2. *For each fixed integer $p \geq 1$, the normalized ratio $\tilde{A}_n(2p) = F_n(2p) R_n(2p)$ admits the asymptotic expansion*

$$\tilde{A}_n(2p) = 1 - \frac{p}{n} + \frac{2p^2 - p + 1}{4n^2} - \frac{4p^4 - 6p^3 + 10p^2 - 3p + 1}{24pn^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right), \quad n \rightarrow \infty,$$

where the coefficients arise entirely from the Stirling expansion of the factorial ratio $F_n(2p)$, and the correction factor $R_n(2p)$ contributes only exponentially small terms.

Proof. By definition

$$F_n(2p) = \frac{(2p(n-1)+p)!(2pn)!}{(2pn+p)!(2p(n-1))!} = \frac{\Gamma(2pn-p+1)\Gamma(2pn+1)}{\Gamma(2pn-2p+1)\Gamma(2pn+p+1)}.$$

Set $z = 2pn$. Then

$$\log F_n(2p) = \log \Gamma(z+1) + \log \Gamma(z-p+1) - \log \Gamma(z-2p+1) - \log \Gamma(z+p+1).$$

We now apply the classical Stirling expansion for the gamma function (see [11, §5.11.1]):

$$\log \Gamma(z+\alpha) = \left(z + \alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right) \log z - z + \frac{1}{2} \log(2\pi) + \frac{\alpha^2 - \alpha}{2z} + \frac{-2\alpha^3 + 3\alpha^2 - \alpha}{12z^2} + O\left(\frac{1}{z^3}\right). \quad (8)$$

Substituting $\alpha \in \{1, 1-p, 1-2p, 1+p\}$ into (8), inserting these into the above expression for $\log F_n(2p)$, and simplifying (using $z = 2pn$) yields an expansion of the form

$$\log F_n(2p) = \frac{a_1}{n} + \frac{a_2}{n^2} + \frac{a_3}{n^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right), \quad n \rightarrow \infty,$$

with

$$a_1 = -p, \quad a_2 = \frac{1-p}{4}, \quad a_3 = \frac{-4p^2 + 3p - 1}{24p}.$$

Next we exponentiate this expansion. Writing

$$\log F_n(2p) = \frac{a_1}{n} + \frac{a_2}{n^2} + \frac{a_3}{n^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right)$$

and using the series for the exponential function,

$$\exp\left(\frac{a_1}{n} + \frac{a_2}{n^2} + \frac{a_3}{n^3} + \dots\right) = 1 + \frac{c_1}{n} + \frac{c_2}{n^2} + \frac{c_3}{n^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right),$$

the coefficients satisfy

$$c_1 = a_1, \quad c_2 = a_2 + \frac{a_1^2}{2}, \quad c_3 = a_3 + a_1 a_2 + \frac{a_1^3}{6}.$$

Substituting a_1, a_2, a_3 gives

$$c_1 = -p, \quad c_2 = \frac{2p^2 - p + 1}{4}, \quad c_3 = -\frac{4p^4 - 6p^3 + 10p^2 - 3p + 1}{24p}.$$

Hence

$$F_n(2p) = 1 - \frac{p}{n} + \frac{2p^2 - p + 1}{4n^2} - \frac{4p^4 - 6p^3 + 10p^2 - 3p + 1}{24pn^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right).$$

Finally, by Theorem 3.1 we have $R_n(2p) = 1 + O(\rho^{-n})$ for some $\rho > 1$, so $R_n(2p)$ contributes only an exponentially small factor and no powers of n^{-1} . Therefore

$$\tilde{A}_n(2p) = F_n(2p) R_n(2p)$$

admits the same algebraic asymptotic expansion in powers of n^{-1} as $F_n(2p)$, which is exactly the formula stated in Theorem 3.2. \square

Example 3.3 (Small even arguments $s = 2, 4, 6$). For $p = 1, 2, 3$ the unit-correction term satisfies $R_n(2p) \equiv 1$, so

$$\tilde{A}_n(2p) = F_n(2p)$$

holds identically.

$p = 1$. In this case

$$F_n(2) = \frac{2n - 1}{2n + 1},$$

and a straightforward expansion yields

$$\tilde{A}_n(2) = 1 - \frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{2n^2} - \frac{1}{4n^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right).$$

$p = 2$. In this case

$$F_n(4) = \frac{(2n - 1)(4n - 3)}{(2n + 1)(4n + 1)},$$

so that

$$\tilde{A}_n(4) = 1 - \frac{2}{n} + \frac{7}{4n^2} - \frac{17}{16n^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right).$$

$p = 3$. Since

$$F_n(6) = \frac{(2n - 1)(3n - 2)(6n - 5)}{(2n + 1)(3n + 1)(6n + 1)},$$

we obtain

$$\tilde{A}_n(6) = 1 - \frac{3}{n} + \frac{4}{n^2} - \frac{61}{18n^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right).$$

These low-weight cases illustrate Theorem 3.1 in the degenerate situation where $R_n(2p) \equiv 1$: the entire $1/n$ expansion of $\tilde{A}_n(2p)$ is already contained in the factorial ratio $F_n(2p)$.

3.4 Example: the case $s = 8$

We illustrate the above theory at $p = 4$. From the combinatorial formulas of Section 2, the set of units $\{\Psi(\varepsilon)\}$ contains a unique dominant orbit represented by

$$X = 1 + \sqrt{2}, \quad |X| > 1,$$

and all other units have strictly smaller modulus $< |X|$. Since $3 + 2\sqrt{2} = X^2$, the explicit evaluations of $t(\{8\}_n)$ and $\zeta(\{8\}_n)$ become [1]

$$t(\{8\}_n) = \frac{\pi^{8n}}{2^{2n+1}(8n)!} (X^{4n} + X^{-4n}),$$

$$\zeta(\{8\}_n) = \frac{8(2\pi)^{8n}}{2^{2n+1}(8n+4)!} (X^{4n+2} + X^{-4n-2}).$$

Therefore

$$A_n(8) = \frac{\zeta(\{8\}_n)}{\zeta(\{8\}_{n-1})} \frac{t(\{8\}_{n-1})}{t(\{8\}_n)}, \quad \tilde{A}_n(8) = 2^{-8} A_n(8),$$

admits the factorization

$$\tilde{A}_n(8) = F_n(8) R_n(8),$$

where the factorial term is

$$F_n(8) = \frac{(2n-1)(4n-3)(8n-7)(8n-5)}{(2n+1)(4n+1)(8n+1)(8n+3)}.$$

Explicit unit correction. The dominant-subdominant decomposition of $t(\{8\}_n)$ and $\zeta(\{8\}_n)$ leads to the following explicit closed form:

$$R_n(8) = \frac{(X^8 + X^{8n})(X^{8n+4} + 1)}{X^4(X^4 + X^{8n})(X^{8n} + 1)} = \frac{(1 + X^{8n-8})(X^{8n+4} + 1)}{(1 + X^{8n-4})(X^{8n} + 1)}, \quad X = 1 + \sqrt{2}.$$

Since $|X| > 1$ is the unique dominant modulus and every other unit satisfies $|\Psi(\varepsilon)| < |X|$, Theorem 3.1 implies

$$R_n(8) = 1 + O(X^{-8n}).$$

Consequently,

$$\tilde{A}_n(8) = F_n(8)(1 + O(X^{-8n})).$$

Asymptotic expansion. Expanding $F_n(8)$ in powers of $1/n$ gives

$$F_n(8) = 1 - \frac{4}{n} + \frac{29}{4n^2} - \frac{263}{32n^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right),$$

and since $R_n(8) = 1 + O(X^{-8n})$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, the same expansion holds for $\tilde{A}_n(8)$:

$$\tilde{A}_n(8) = 1 - \frac{4}{n} + \frac{29}{4n^2} - \frac{263}{32n^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right).$$

3.5 A conjectural odd-argument analogue

We briefly record the first odd case $s = 3$ as a numerical conjecture.

Conjecture 3.4 (The case of odd argument $s = 3$). *The factorial-unit factorization developed in this paper applies only to repeated even arguments $s = 2p$. For the first odd case $s = 3$, numerical computations suggest that the normalized ratio*

$$\tilde{A}_n(3) = 2^{-3} \frac{\zeta(\{3\}_n) t(\{3\}_{n-1})}{\zeta(\{3\}_{n-1}) t(\{3\}_n)}$$

admits an asymptotic expansion in powers of n^{-1} of the form

$$\tilde{A}_n(3) = 1 - \frac{3}{2n} + \frac{c_2(3)}{n^2} + \frac{c_3(3)}{n^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^4}\right), \quad n \rightarrow \infty,$$

for certain real constants $c_2(3)$ and $c_3(3)$. In particular, we conjecture that the coefficient of n^{-1} is

$$\boxed{-\frac{3}{2}},$$

mirroring the pattern $-p/n$ occurring in the even-argument case $s = 2p$. Determining the structural origin of this coefficient for odd arguments remains an open problem.

In contrast to the even-argument case $s = 2p$, the odd case $s = 3$ does not appear to admit a unique dominant algebraic unit in the sense of Section 2.3.2. Rather, several units of equal maximal modulus (or lying on the unit circle) are expected to contribute simultaneously. This breaks the dominance mechanism underlying Theorem 3.1, so that the factorial term alone no longer suffices to explain the leading coefficient in the asymptotic expansion of $\tilde{A}_n(3)$.

4 Conclusion

We have shown that the repeated-index values $\zeta(\{2p\}_n)$ and $t(\{2p\}_n)$ admit exact closed forms derived directly from their cosine and sine product generating functions. These formulas reveal that all such values are governed by the finite set of algebraic units

$$\Psi(\varepsilon) = \sum_{j=1}^p \varepsilon_j e^{\pi i(2j-1)/(2p)}, \quad \varepsilon_j \in \{\pm 1\}.$$

The dihedral symmetry of this unit set produces a unique dominant orbit, and this structural fact yields the canonical factorization

$$\tilde{A}_n(2p) = F_n(2p) R_n(2p),$$

in which $F_n(2p)$ is a rational function of n while the correction term $R_n(2p)$ is exponentially close to 1. Consequently, the entire asymptotic expansion of $\tilde{A}_n(2p)$ in powers of n^{-1} is determined solely by the factorial ratio $F_n(2p)$.

The methods developed here rely only on elementary exponential expansions and root-of-unity symmetries, providing a direct and transparent framework that refines and strengthens previously known structural results in the literature.

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